

AUT – UNIVERSITY TEACHING: BASICS

Module 3: Designing a Teaching Event

After having finished two modules of the Basic Course you are now well equipped for Module 3.

Module 3 “Designing a Teaching Event” is a practice-oriented module that consists of 2 Units: Unit 13 and Unit 14. They are geared toward each other and lead to the successful completion of the module's assignment.

The goal of Module 3 is to deepen your acquired knowledge by designing a concept for a teaching event, e.g. a seminar, a workshop, a blended- or online course, or by revising an existing one that somehow relates to your professional background. This will be accompanied by an individual coaching session with a trainer and by peer feedback which may provide you with additional insight, ideas and perspectives to improve your concept.

→ The detailed assignment can be found at the end of this document.

What will happen in Module 3?

Step 0: Kick-off meeting

Attend the kick-off meeting of Module 3 on Monday, May 9, 2022, from 4 - 6 p.m. local time in Jordan, Lebanon and Syria (3 - 5 p.m. in Germany), via Zoom.

Step 1: Learning about peer feedback in **Unit 13**

Become familiar with the concept of peer feedback using materials in Unit 13. Please go through all activities and tasks. That will allow you to optimally prepare for Unit 14.

Please note:

Unit 13 officially starts on May 9, 2022. In order to give you an opportunity to look into it during the Ramadan break the unit will be activated in Moodle in the first week of April.

Step 2: Drafting the first concept in **Unit 14**

Draft the first version of your concept for peer feedback. It doesn't have to meet all the criteria of the final version yet. It may be shorter and include questions for your peer feedbackers. However, it should provide your peers with a good idea of your concept.

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You can work on a course you plan to conduct in the future or you can revise a course that you taught already in the past. Focus on a part of a whole course, e.g. one unit, one session. If applicable, you may also focus on a whole semester if you plan to revise the whole course (e.g. if you want to change from a face-to-face to an online format).

Deadline for submission: Mai 12, 2022.

The file upload in Moodle will open up on May 2, 2022.

Step 3: Giving and receiving peer feedback

Give each other peer feedback on your first drafts. Use the peer feedback criteria mentioned in Unit 13. You are supposed to work in groups of three. (The formation of the groups will be explained in Moodle.) Make sure to finish the peer feedback process in time for revision of the concepts by the trainer.

Deadline for submission: Mai 17, 2022.

The file upload in Moodle will open up on May 2, 2022.

Step 4: Revision of the concept after peer feedback and submission of your final concept

Revise your concept taking into consideration comments and suggestions from your colleague. Hand in your final versions of the concept for revision by the trainer.

Deadline for submission: Mai 23, 2022. If you are finished before that you are welcome to submit the file earlier.

The file upload in Moodle will open up on May 16, 2022.

Step 5: Feedback on your concept and coaching

In the period between May 23 and June 8 you will receive feedback from your trainer Katharina Günther – either in written form or as recorded verbal feedback. At this time we will also ask you to sign up for one online coaching session for the discussion of your concept. In this session you can ask questions about the received feedback or about other issues concerning your concept. If you don't manage to arrange an online session you have the opportunity to ask final questions about the received feedback via email as well.

Step 6: Final event of Module 3

Attend the final event of Module 3. The date of the final event is to be announced.

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Module 3 Assignment

Draft a concept for a teaching event, e.g. a seminar, a workshop, a blended- or online course, that somehow relates to your professional background. You can work on a course you plan to conduct in the future or you can revise a course that you taught already in the past. Focus on a part of a whole course, e.g. one unit, one session. If applicable, you may also focus on a whole semester if you plan to revise the whole course (e.g. if you want to change from a face-to-face to an online-format).

You will at first receive –and give– peer feedback on your concepts, then revise your own concept and finally get feedback on the revised concept from your trainer including an individual one-hour coaching session.

The concept should include the following:

- context: target group, group size, subject, learning outcomes, content, duration, possibly form of assessment, context (e.g. as part of a module, learning environment, institutional requirements)
- didactical design, including references to at least one topic from module 1 or 2; e.g. description of methods, media usage, learning activities etc.
- reasoning for your choice of didactical design (e.g. by referring to a theoretical background from module 1 or 2), consider the questions for reflection from modules 1 and 2
- you may include questions for your peer reviewers or the reviewing trainer about aspects you are unsure about
- in case you are revising an old course: Why do you think revision is necessary? What is the aim of the revision and what are possible challenges?

Formal requirements:

- size: approx. 1200 words, absolute maximum: 1500 words (excluding cover page and bibliography)
- Use complete sentences for your description. You may add key points, pictures or tables when it serves the purpose of illustration / visualisation. You may for example use the handout “Didactic Lesson Plan” (Unit 3).
- cover page that includes your name, your email address and the name of your concept / teaching event
- bibliography

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